

Molecular Docking Analysis to explore the Antihypertensive Potential of *Cynodon dactylon*

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Abstract

The Siddha system of traditional medicine has long been employed in managing a wide array of diseases, particularly non-communicable disorders. Hypertension, a prevalent global health issue, affects over 220 million individuals in India and approximately 1.28 billion worldwide. Although various synthetic antihypertensive medications are available, they are often associated with adverse side effects and complications during prolonged use. This study aims to identify potential antihypertensive compounds present in the root of *Cynodon dactylon* (Family: Poaceae) and evaluate their molecular interactions with hypertension-associated targets through docking studies. Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme (ACE), a key regulator in blood pressure control, was selected as the target protein. Bioactive phytochemicals extracted from the root of *Cynodon dactylon* were structurally prepared using ChemSpider. Molecular docking was performed using ArgusLab software to evaluate the binding affinities of these compounds. Among the phytoconstituents, cinnamic acid—a phenolic compound isolated from *Cynodon dactylon* roots—demonstrated a strong binding interaction with ACE, suggesting a potential antihypertensive activity. Molecular docking results suggest that the key bioactive constituents in *Cynodon dactylon* exhibit promising interactions with hypertension-related target proteins. These findings support the potential use of this herb in the development of novel antihypertensive formulations within Siddha pharmacology.

Key words: *Cynodon dactylon*, Antihypertensive Activity, Molecular Docking, Siddha Medicine

Introduction:

The Siddha system of medicine is one of India's indigenous medical traditions, with origins traced back around 10,000 BC in the Dravidian civilization. The term "Siddha" derives from the root word "Siddhi", meaning attainment of perfection, emphasizing a holistic view of health that integrates physical, psychological, social and spiritual well-being. The Siddha system of traditional medicine has long been employed in managing a wide array of diseases, particularly non-communicable disorders. Hypertension, a prevalent global health issue, affects 220 million individuals in India and approximately 1.28 billion worldwide. Hypertension, more commonly known as high blood pressure, is a chronic medical condition wherein the blood pressure remains raised in the arterial blood vessels. According to the Global Burden of Disease Study, over the last couple of decades, there has been a sharp rise in the prevalence of hypertension, which is largely driven by senior populations and changes in lifestyle variables such as food, physical sedentary behavior, and raised body mass index(BMI). Cardiovascular complications like Myocardial damage or heart attacks, stroke, and renal failure and developed by persistent hypertension. The annual estimation of the WHO reported that hypertension causes 9.4 million fatalities, accounting for about 12.8% of the global mortality rate. The Angiotensin-converting enzyme(ACE) is crucial for modulating clinical hypertension by regulating vascular flexibility and balancing the salt content. Additionally angiotensin II affects heart and kidney vascular function and increases the reabsorption of salt and water, all of these subsidizing the increase of blood pressure. Disrupting in these pathways can result in the development of chronic hypertension and organ damage. The angiotensin-converting enzyme(ACE) is a two-domain dipeptidylcarboxypeptidase that has a direct participation in the control of blood pressure by hydrolysis of angiotensin I to produce angiotensin II. Angiotensin II is a powerful vasoconstrictor and stimulant for the secretion of aldosterone, an event causing an elevation of blood pressure and fluid retention. The deregulation of this system will lead to cardiovascular disorders such as heart failure, myocardial infarction and hypertension. ACE inhibitors such as captopril, enalapril and lisinopril are used to prevent the generation of angiotensin II in the treatment of these disorders. Medicines of this kind are quite effective; they have certain limitations, including potential adverse effects and individual sensitivity to medicines. Therefore it requires searching for non-toxic natural products. In the past few decades, a lot of investigation has been done on medicinal plants for treating cardiovascular diseases, providing insight into natural resources for ACE inhibition. *Cynodon dactylon* is an herbaceous Poaceae family member particularly, the roots and leaves of this plant have been widely used in folk medicine to treat several illness. Molecular docking is a specifically attractive tactic in the lead identification phase of a compound. It helps researchers screen large databases in a short time, select the probable molecule, and enhances the lead molecule for better efficacy and safety. In the case of hypertension, phenolic compounds offer promising avenues for developing novel ACE inhibitors. By elucidating the binding interactions and evaluating pharmacokinetic properties, these studies enhance our understanding of the therapeutic potential of natural compounds. The docking process involves prediction the ligand's conformation and assessing binding affinity, providing insight into drug-receptor interactions. This technique has become essential in modern research, allowing for the rapid visualization of complex structures and enabling a more rational approach to drug design based on the three-dimensional structure of receptor sites. Together, the Siddha system's holistic approach and the advancements in

molecular docking underscore the importance of integrating traditional and modern scientific practices in tackling health issues in India.

Objective:

The components in root of *Cynodon dactylon* were examined in this study for their potential as a medical agent for the control of hypertension using docking experiments. The function of the target protein human Acetylcholinesterase will be hampered if phytochemicals bind to the core amino acids (Arg 296, Phe 295, Ser 293, Leu 289, Val 294, Trp 286, Tyr 341) of the target by forming hydrogen bonds. Thus, phytochemicals that block the action of the target enzyme Acetylcholinesterase may have the potential as a treatment for hypertension.

Methodology:

Cynodon dactylon was taken as trial drug from Siddha Literatures “*Gunapadam mooligai vaguppu*” for the management of Hypertension.

Indications:

Mukutra keedu, Eelai, Kan noi, Kan pugaichal, Thalai noi, Kuruthiazhal.

Software used for docking:

- 1.Chemsketch software.
- 2.Autodock 4.1 version.

Molecular Docking Studies

Protein-ligand docking studies of Cinnamic acid and Captopril was evaluated in order to investigate the interaction between the active site of Acetylcholinesterase and the ligands on Chemskth software.

Ligand preparation

The ligand Cinnamic acid and captopril was prepared using Chemsketh (Hunter *et al.*, 1997). The mol format of the corresponding 3D structures was given as the ligand input file for AutoDock v4.1 for energy minimization and subjected to a subsequent docking method. All the properties of the compounds were analyzed for the validation of ligand structure.

Fig 1: 2D structure of Cinnamic Acid

Fig 2: 2D structure of Captopril

Receptor structure characterization and active site prediction

The Crystal Structure of Human Acetylcholinesterase (PDB: 4PQE) was obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) (<http://www.rcsb.org/pdb>) (Byth et al., 2004). The predicted hydrophilic, hydrophobic regions and active site region of receptor using automated method in Discovery Studio. The active sites of the protein was predicted by automated receptor cavity method using cavity detection and eraser algorithm which reveals the key residues in the target proteins which are responsible for interaction of ligand molecule (Sarikurkcü *et al.*, 2008).

Fig 3: Receptor (PDB: 4PQE) active sites were predicted using Discovery studio visualizer. Protein residues are represented by solid ribbon style, respectively. Active site regions are represented as a yellow smear model.

Autodock

A ligand and protein preparation method was performed using AutoDock v4.1 software. In this study Lamarckian genetic algorithm (LGA) was followed. The active site was defined using autogrid. The specified grid box provides enough space for the ligand translation, 50° for rotation and the maximum number of energy evaluations was set to 2,000,000. Thirty runs were performed. For each of the 30 independent runs, a maximum number of 27,000 GA operations were generated on a single population of 50 individuals (Morris et al., 2009).

Table 1 : Interaction Data for Cinnamic acid

S.NO	Mode	Binding Affinity	RMSD Upper bound	RMSD Lower bound
1	0	-6.9Kcal/mol	0	0
2	1	-6.6Kcal/mol	9.625	8.513
3	2	-6.4Kcal/mol	2.441	1.715
4	3	-6.3Kcal/mol	6.812	5.313
5	4	-6.3Kcal/mol	9.639	7.057
6	5	-5.9Kcal/mol	8.837	7.416
7	6	-5.7Kcal/mol	2.422	1.752
8	7	-5.6Kcal/mol	5.679	4.043
9	8	-5.6Kcal/mol	31.84	30.673

Figure 4: Ligands binding predicted using AUTODOCK. Protein residues (blue line) and ligand (green color) are represented by thin and sticks, respectively. Ligand binding regions are represented as ball and stick model. Hydrogen bonds are shown in yellow dashed solid lines, respectively. Ligand shown interaction with the receptor (PDB: 4PQE) at O (ARG296) by forming Hydrogen bond with the distance measured as 2.3157 Å.

Table 2 : Interaction Data for Captopril

S.NO	Mode	Binding Affinity	RMSD Upper bound	RMSD Lower bound
1	0	-6.5Kcal/mol	0	0
2	1	-6.3Kcal/mol	3.267	2.516
3	2	-5.9Kcal/mol	7.845	6.969
4	3	-5.8Kcal/mol	8.886	7.371
5	4	-5.5Kcal/mol	8.138	7.296
6	5	-5.5Kcal/mol	23.086	21.87
7	6	-5.3Kcal/mol	10.45	9.02
8	7	-5.2Kcal/mol	9.982	8.702
9	8	-5.2Kcal/mol	9.882	8.302

Figure 5: Ligands binding predicted using AUTODOCK. Protein residues (blue line) and ligand (green color) are represented by thin and sticks, respectively. Ligand binding regions are represented as ball and stick model. Hydrogen bonds are shown in yellow dashed solid lines, respectively. Ligand shown three mode interaction with the receptor (PDB: 4PQE) at SER125 and TYR124 by forming Hydrogen bond with the distance measured as 2.24774, 2.34021 Å and 2.44917 Å respectively.

Compounds having similar structures similar to Cinnamic acid:

1. Syringic acid

2. Isooreintin

3. Arundoin

4. Luteolin

5. Apigenin

6. Orientin

7. Ascorbic acid

8. beta-Ionone

9. Furfuryl alcohol

10. Furfural

11. Vanillic acid

12. Docosanoic acid

13. Palmitic acid

14. Phenylacetaldehyde

15. Isovitexin

16. Tritriacontane

17. 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid

18. Triglochinin

19. Friedelin

20. beta-Carotene

21. Ergometrine

22. Ergometrinine

23. Ferulic acid

24. 4-Hydroxycinnamic acid

25. Vitexin

26. beta-Sitosterol

27. Tricin

28. 6,10,14-Trimethylpentadecan-2-one

29. Stigmasterol acetate

30. 2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)propanoic acid

31. beta-Sitosterol-d-glucoside

32. Apigenin

33. Phytol

Discussion:**Table 3 : Comparison of Interaction Data of Cinnamic acid and Captopril**

S.NO	Ligand	Binding Affinity	RMSD Upper bound	RMSD Lower bound
1	Cinnamic Acid	-6.9Kcal/mol	0	0
2	Captopril	-6.5Kcal/mol	0	0

Molecular docking analysis of isolated compound Cinnamic acid demonstrated a docking score of -6.9 kcal/mol, outperforming the standard drug Captopril (-6.5 kcal/mol), suggesting its potential as a promising ACE inhibitor.

Conclusion:

The molecular docking analysis revealed that Cinnamic acid demonstrated a superior docking score (binding affinity) of -6.9 kcal/mol when compared to the reference drug Captopril (-6.5 kcal/mol) against the target protein, Human Acetylcholinesterase (PDB: 4PQE). This favorable binding energy suggests that Cinnamic acid, the bioactive compound identified in *Cynodon dactylon* root, exhibits a promising antihypertensive potential, likely through potent inhibition of the target enzyme. Further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies are warranted to validate this therapeutic potential.

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